

Fuzzy Measurement Algorithm for Fault Detection in the Hydrogenerator

Saša D. Milić¹, Blagoje M. Babić^{2,1}, Aleksandar Ž. Rakić²

¹University of Belgrade, Electrical Engineering Institute 'Nikola Tesla', Belgrade, Serbia,
s_milic@yahoo.com, blagojebabic@gmail.com

²University of Belgrade, School of Electrical Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia,
rakic@etf.rs

Abstract—Fault detection involves the detection, location, and identification of faults. Three types of unbalances (mechanical, hydraulic and magnetic) can occur in hydrogenerators. There are two main reasons for the existence of magnetic unbalance: shorted turns in the windings of the rotor poles and geometric asymmetry of the air gap. In this study, the authors propose a novel fuzzy measurement algorithm for fault detection in the hydrogenerator. The proposed algorithm has been developed with aim to detect the presence and cause of the magnetic unbalance and vibrations of the hydrogenerator. The study is based on fuzzy theory and three measurement methods for measuring inner and outer magnetic fluxes and measuring mechanical vibrations. The fuzzy algorithm has to ensure, in situ and real time, magnetic and vibration monitoring and fault detection and as such it is suitable for implementation in on-line and real time monitoring systems. The main benefit of the proposed solution lies in the support for the optimal decision making regarding the predictive maintenance.

Keywords - hydrogenerator, fuzzy measurement algorithm, fault detection, magnetic flux

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogenerators are exposed to severe stresses and loads of electrical, mechanical, hydraulic and thermal nature, resulting in a large number of potential failures [1].

The proposed fuzzy measurement algorithm (FMA) belongs to the type of fault detection algorithms and is based on measurement of the main radial magnetic flux in the air gap, leakage radial magnetic flux on the stator housing and mechanical vibrations on the upper guide bearing of hydrogenerators. These three

concepts are combined and used to complement each other.

FMA has been developed with the aim to detect the presence of the magnetic unbalance of the hydrogenerator. Magnetic unbalance will at least reduce operating efficiency and in more severe cases can lead to heavy damage [2].

There are two main reasons for the existence of magnetic unbalance: shorted turns in the windings of the rotor poles and geometric asymmetry of the air gap. The magnetic flux in the air gap, corresponding to the pole with the shorted turns, is smaller in comparison with the magnetic flux of other poles [3, 4]. Oscillations of the magnetic flux in the air gap can also be caused by the air gap asymmetry, which is most often the consequence either of the eccentricity of the rotor or irregularly shaped rotor/stator. Due to changes in the length of air gap, the magnetic flux in hydrogenerator also changes. The change in the magnetic flux density in the air gap (with generators which have a different degree of rotor eccentricity) was discussed in [5].

Generally speaking, the mechanical vibrations recorded on the housings of guide generator bearings are indicator of the presence of mechanical and magnetic rotor unbalance. Magnetic unbalance changes the vibration levels in the regimes of no-load unexcited/excited operations. The levels of the vibrations that are belong to the range of the normal operation are given in [6].

II. FUZZY MEASUREMENT ALGORITHM (FMA)

With the aim of a comprehensive analysis, FMA takes into account the value of mechanical

vibrations of the upper guide bearing and magnetic flux (Fig.1).

The algorithm consists of two separate parts. The first one takes into account magnetic and vibration measurements and the second one is useful for fuzzy approaching in the making decision.

Fig. 1 Fuzzy measurement algorithm (FMA)

III. FUZZY LOGIC AND MAKING DECISION

Conventional system theory relies on crisp mathematical models of systems. However, for a large number of practical problems, which are described by linguistic forms, fuzzy logic theory is more suitable. According to the above mentioned, modeling the decision-making

process often relies on a fuzzy-based decision model applications.

The pioneer and founder of the fuzzy logic theory is Lotfi A. Zadeh [1, 2]. He introduced fuzzy sets for describing ambiguity and fuzziness of the linguistic representation of certain physical phenomena and technological processes. This study presents a fuzzy-measurement algorithm (FMA) which is based on fuzzy logic theory and fault detection methodology related to generators in hydro power plants.

A. FUZZY LOGIC SYSTEM (FLS)

Let X be the universe of discourse and its elements be denoted as x . Fuzzy set A of universe X is defined by function $\mu_A(x)$ called the membership function of set A :

$$f_A(x) : X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}, f_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fuzzy set A of universe X is defined by function $\mu_A(x)$ called the membership function of set A :

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A(x) &= 1 \text{ if } x \text{ is totally in } A \\ \mu_A(x) : X \rightarrow [0,1], \mu_A(x) &= 0 \text{ if } x \text{ is not in } A \\ 0 < \mu_A(x) < 1 & \text{ if } x \text{ is partly in } A \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This presentation of set allows a continuum of possible choices. For any element x of universe X , membership function $\mu_A(x)$ equals the degree to which x is an element of set A . This degree, a value between 0 and 1, represents the degree of membership, also called membership value, of element x in set A (Fuzzy Logic lecture – A.Rakić).

The fuzzy logic system (FLS) was first proposed by Mamdani [3,4] and then has been widely applied in many practical applications in which there are many uncertainties. In addition to the Mamdani FLS, today the most commonly used system is Takagi-Sugeno FLS (TS-FLS) [5,6]. These systems differ in the structure, but have the same rules (if-then).

For a Mamdani FLS with MISO structure (multiple input, single output) the n th rule can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rule}^n : & \text{IF } x_1 \text{ is } F_1^n \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } x_m \text{ is } F_m^n \\ & \text{THEN } y \text{ is } Q^n, n = 1, \dots, N \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where:

n - n th rule

m - number of inputs
 F_m^n - antecedent fuzzy set
 Q^n - consequent fuzzy set

For a TS-FLS with MISO structure (multiple input, single output) which uses function of input variables as rule consequents, the n th rule can be expressed as:

$$\text{Rule}^n : \text{IF } x_1 \text{ is } F_1^n \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } x_m \text{ is } F_m^n \quad (4)$$

$$\text{THEN } y = y^n(x) \equiv y^n(x_1, \dots, x_m), \quad n = 1, \dots, N$$

where $y^n(x)$ is a function (linear or nonlinear) of the inputs variables.

For a TS-FLS with MISO structure (multiple input, single output) which uses linear function of input variables as rule consequents, the n th rule can be expressed as:

$$\text{Rule}^n : \text{IF } x_1 \text{ is } F_1^n \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } x_m \text{ is } F_m^n \quad (5)$$

$$\text{THEN } y = y^n(x) = c_0^n + c_1^n \cdot x_1 + \dots + c_m^n \cdot x_m, \quad n = 1, \dots, N$$

where c_0^n, \dots, c_m^n are the consequent parameters.

The main shortcomings of A and B is that they do not take into account the connection between inputs and consequents. Therefore, care should be taken in the selection of parameters for the fuzzy rules.

FLS is composed of four main components (Fig.2): fuzzifier, fuzzy rules, inference engine, and defuzzifier [20].

Fig. 2. FLS Type-1

B. Fuzzy Modeling

In this study, for the needs of fuzzy modeling, the following membership functions are used:

1. Triangular-shaped membership function:

$$f(x; a, b, c) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & c \leq x \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

2. Trapezoidal-shaped membership function

$$f(x; a, b, c, d) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ 1, & b \leq x \leq c \\ \frac{d-x}{d-c}, & c \leq x \leq d \\ 0, & d \leq x \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

3. Gaussian curve membership function:

$$f(x; \sigma, c) = e^{-\frac{(x-c)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (8)$$

4. Π -shaped membership function

$$f(x; a, b, c, d) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a \\ 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right)^2, & a \leq x \leq \frac{a+b}{2} \\ 1 - 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-b}{b-a}\right)^2, & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x \leq b \\ 1, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 1 - 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-c}{d-c}\right)^2, & c \leq x \leq \frac{c+d}{2} \\ 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-d}{d-c}\right)^2, & \frac{c+d}{2} \leq x \leq d \\ 0, & x \geq d \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

5. Z-shaped membership function:

$$f(x; a, b) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \leq a \\ 1 - 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right)^2, & a \leq x \leq \frac{a+b}{2} \\ 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-b}{b-a}\right)^2, & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x \leq b \\ 0, & x \geq b \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

6. S-shaped membership function:

$$f(x; a, b) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a \\ 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right)^2, & a \leq x \leq \frac{a+b}{2} \\ 1 - 2 \cdot \left(\frac{x-b}{b-a}\right)^2, & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x \leq b \\ 1, & x \geq b \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

7. Generalized bell-shaped membership function:

$$f(x; a, b, c) = \frac{1}{1 + \left|\frac{x-c}{a}\right|^{2b}} \quad (12)$$

IV. FMA VALIDATION

Measuring part of FMA conducts analysis of magnetic flux. The algorithm also takes into account the parameters of vibration recorded on bearing of hydrogenerator.

Figs. 3 and 4 show the change in magnetic flux in the air gap of the generator and change of leakage magnetic flux of stator in real exploitation [2].

Fig. 3 Change in magnetic flux in the air gap of the full load generator.

Fig. 4 Change of leakage magnetic flux of stator (raw flux) of the full load generator.

Due to shorted turns, there has been a reduction in the value of the magnetic flux of given pole (integrated flux, see Fig. 3) in relation to the magnetic flux of the other poles for approximately 2.7%.

The FFT analysis of leakage magnetic flux of stators of generator was performed. Increase of value (of 21.41db) of harmonic with frequency 16.66Hz (where rotor mechanical rotating frequency is: 8.33Hz) in the spectrum of leakage flux, was the consequence of existence of shorted turns. Amplitude of mechanical

vibrations (the peak value of amplitude of basic components per number of rotations ($A_{0\text{-peak}}$)) reached approximately $5/12\mu\text{m}$ (no-load unexcited/excited operation) on upper generator bearing. It can be concluded that magnetic unbalance exists. In the regime of maximum load (40MW) measured value is approximately $15\mu\text{m}$.

The fuzzy model (Figs. 5-7) was made in MatLab and verified the previously presented measured results of vibration and magnetic fluxes (inner and outer).

Fig. 5 Condition assessment is a function of outer and inner flux.

Fig. 6 Condition assessment is a function of outer flux and vibration.

Fig. 7 Condition assessment is a function of inner flux and vibration.

Despite the detected failure, it can be concluded that there is no significant increase in vibrations.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a novel fuzzy measurement algorithm for fault detection in the hydrogenerator with the aim to combine the advantages of fuzzy logic with the advantages of improved measurement methods for measuring vibrations and inner and outer magnetic fluxes in the hydrogenerator.

Two types of fuzzy logic systems were considered (Mamdani and Takagi-Sugeno) and then applied.

The last part of the study discusses the validation of the proposed fuzzy-measurement algorithm that was carried out using appropriate software (MATLAB) and results obtained in real exploitation (in situ).

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